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A QSPR-Enhanced MCDM Technique Utilizes Degree-Based Topological Indices to Evaluate Breast Cancer Drugs Based on Multiple Criteria

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Abstract

Objectives: Breast cancer continues to demand improved analytical approaches for assessing available therapeutic agents. This study aims to analyze approved breast cancer drugs using graph-theoretical descriptors and assess their relationship with key physicochemical properties through Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship (QSPR) and Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) techniques. **Method:** Twenty-two approved breast cancer drugs were modeled as molecular graphs. Revan degree-based topological indices were computed and used as descriptors. Six physicochemical properties, namely molecular weight, boiling point, flash point, complexity, exact mass and topological polar surface area, were examined. Their dependence on structural characteristics was analyzed using Multiple Linear Regression. Furthermore, MCDM techniques, namely TOPSIS and VIKOR, were applied to rank the drugs based on their performance. **Findings:** The outcomes indicate that several of the calculated descriptors are strongly associated with the selected properties. In particular, molecular complexity exhibited a very high correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.981$ along with an acceptable prediction error ($RMSE = 62.087$), highlighting the explanatory strength of the proposed indices. To obtain an overall comparison of drug performance, the ranking techniques TOPSIS and VIKOR were implemented. Both methods yielded comparable rankings, with Abraxane, Everolimus, and Docetaxel consistently placed among the leading candidates. **Novelty:** This study integrates Revan degree-based indices with QSPR modeling and MCDM techniques to provide a comprehensive and structured framework for evaluating breast cancer drugs. The combined approach enhances predictive accuracy and supports effective drug prioritization.

Keywords: Revan indices; Breast cancer drugs; Multiple Linear Regression; QSPR analysis; MCDM techniques

1 Introduction

Breast cancer continues to be one of the most commonly diagnosed malignancies and represents a significant cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. Nevertheless, the heterogeneous nature of the disease still demands advanced computational and mathematical approaches for effective drug investigation and predictive analysis⁽¹⁾. Chemical graph theory provides an efficient framework for representing molecular structures as graphs composed of vertices and edges, where structural characteristics are quantified using topological indices^{(2), (3)}. Among these descriptors, degree-based topological indices have attracted considerable attention in pharmaceutical and anticancer drug research due to their applications in Quantitative Structure–Property Relationship (QSPR) analysis for predicting physicochemical and biological properties.

Several studies have demonstrated the importance of degree-based topological indices and graph theoretical approaches in QSPR analysis of anticancer^{(4), (5)}, skin cancer⁽⁶⁾, blood cancer⁽⁷⁾, lung cancer⁽⁸⁾, and breast cancer drugs^{(9), (10), (11)}. Python-based topological techniques were also applied for predictive QSPR analysis of anticancer compounds⁽¹²⁾. Novel regression-based topological descriptors were additionally utilized for anti-breast cancer drug analysis⁽¹³⁾. Coindex and metric-based approaches also showed promising applications in breast cancer therapeutics^{(14), (15), (16)}. Furthermore, VIKOR-based multi-criteria decision-making methods have been effectively utilized for target-focused anticancer drug screening⁽¹⁷⁾, analyzing specific lung disorders⁽¹⁸⁾, and assessing drug pharmacokinetic properties across multi-criteria frameworks⁽¹⁹⁾. Many earlier studies represent single, double, and triple bonds identically as single edges in molecular graphs, which may reduce important structural information and affect the predictive performance of degree-based descriptors. Therefore, separate representation of bond multiplicities can provide a more realistic molecular framework for QSPR analysis of breast cancer drugs. In this study, twenty-two breast cancer drugs are investigated using modified molecular graphs in which single, double, and triple bonds are represented by one, two, and three edges, respectively. Based on these graph structures, several Revan-type topological indices are calculated and utilized for QSPR analysis of important physicochemical properties. In addition, Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution), and VIKOR (Vise Kriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje) methods are employed to evaluate and rank the selected drugs. The proposed framework integrates chemical graph theory, Revan-type topological descriptors, QSPR modeling, and MCDM approaches, this study aims to provide a more comprehensive structural and predictive analysis of breast cancer drugs.

2 Methodology

2.1 Preliminaries

A molecular structure can be represented by a graph in which atoms correspond to vertices and chemical bonds correspond to edges. Such graphical representations constitute the foundation of chemical graph theory and are widely used in structural characterization and drug discovery. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a finite and connected graph, where $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ denote the vertex set and edge set, respectively. The degree of a vertex $x \in V(G)$, denoted by $d_G(x)$, is defined as the number of vertices adjacent to x . The minimum and maximum degrees of G are represented by $\delta(G)$ and $\Delta(G)$, respectively. The Revan vertex degree of a vertex x is defined as $r_G(x) = \Delta(G) + \delta(G) - d_G(x)$. For an edge $xy \in E(G)$, the revan degree is determined using the Revan degree of its end vertices x and y . Various Revan-type indices have been introduced to quantify structural characteristics of graphs.

2.2 Dataset Description

In this study, the Revan-based topological indices were computed for twenty-two clinically approved breast cancer drugs, namely Abemaciclib, Abraxane, Anastrozole, Capecitabine, Cyclophosphamide, Doxorubicin, Everolimus, Exemestane, Fluorouracil, Fulvestrant, Ixabepilone, Lapatinib, Letrozole, Megestrol Acetate, Methotrexate, Olaparib, Docetaxel, Palbociclib, Ribociclib, Talazoparib, Tamoxifen, and Thiotepa. For each drug, the required physicochemical properties are molecular weight, boiling point, flash point, complexity, exact mass, and topological polar surface area were collected from established chemical databases, including PubChem, Chems spider and Chemsr.c. These descriptors serve as independent variables and their properties were considered as dependent variables within QSPR modeling framework. The molecular structures were obtained from PubChem and converted into molecular graphs for the computation of the corresponding indices. The chemical structures of all 22 investigated breast cancer drugs are provided in the supplementary file.

Topological Indices	Mathematical Formula
First Revan index ⁽²⁰⁾	$R_1(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} [r_G(x) + r_G(y)]$
Second Revan index ⁽²⁰⁾	$R_2(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} [r_G(x)r_G(y)]$
First Hyper- Revan index ⁽²⁰⁾	$HR_1(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} [r_G(x) + r_G(y)]^2$
Second Hyper-Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$HR_2(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} [r_G(x)r_G(y)]^2$
1 st Modified Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	${}^mR_1(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{1}{[r_G(x)+r_G(y)]}$
2 st Modified Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	${}^mR_2(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{1}{[r_G(x)r_G(y)]}$
Sum Connectivity Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$SR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_G(x)+r_G(y)}}$
Product Connectivity Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$PR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{r_G(x)r_G(y)}}$
F-Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$FR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} [r_G(x)^2 + r_G(y)^2]$
Atom Bond Connectivity Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$ABCR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \sqrt{\frac{[r_G(x)+r_G(y)-2]}{r_G(x)r_G(y)}}$
Geometric Arithmetic Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$GAR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{2\sqrt{r_G(x)r_G(y)}}{r_G(x)+r_G(y)}$
Harmonic Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$HR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{2}{[r_G(x)+r_G(y)]}$
Symmetric Division Revan Index ⁽²⁰⁾	$SDR(G) = \sum_{xy \in E(G)} \frac{r_G(x)}{r_G(y)} + \frac{r_G(y)}{r_G(x)}$

2.3 Calculation of Revan Degree-Based Topological Indices

The Revan topological indices of molecular graph (A) for abemaciclib as follows: $R_1(A) = 190$, $R_2(A) = 176$, $HR_1(A) = 782$, $HR_2(A) = 906$, ${}^mR_1(A) = 15.120$, ${}^mR_2(A) = 21.556$, $SR(A) = 27.428$, $PR(A) = 31.815$, $FR(A) = 430$, $ABCR(A) = 33.189$, $GAR(A) = 48.380$, $HR(A) = 30.219$, $SDR(A) = 126.833$.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the molecular graph (A) of abemaciclib consists of 37 vertices and 51 edges. Nine partitions are created from the edge set $E(A)$ according to vertex degree:

Fig 1. Chemical structure and Molecular graph of Abemaciclib

Table 1. Revan edge partition of Abemaciclib

$(r_A(x), r_A(y))/xy \in E(A)$	(4, 3)	(4, 2)	(4, 1)	(3, 3)	(3, 2)	(3, 1)	(2, 2)	(2, 1)	(1, 1)
No. of Edges	1	2	3	2	6	3	5	24	5

The results are obtained using Revan-based topological indices formula and revan edge partitions (Table 1). Corresponding results for the remaining drug compounds are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

2.4 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regression is a statistical technique employed to characterize the relationship between one dependent variable and several independent variables through a linear equation. The general multiple linear regression equation,

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1(RI)_1 + \beta_2(RI)_2 + \dots + \beta_n(RI)_n + \varepsilon$$

where P is physicochemical properties, β_0 is the intercept (constant term), $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the regression coefficients, ε represent the error term and $(RI)_i$ denotes a revan topological index. Twenty-two breast cancer drugs and six physicochemical

characteristics are associated through multiple linear regression analysis using revan index values. The physical characteristics considered in this investigation are the following parameters: molecular weight (MW g/mol), boiling point (BP^0 C at 760mmHg), flash point (FP^0 C), complexity (COM), exact mass (EM) and topological polar surface area (TPSA). Revan indices for the molecular graphs of 22 pharmaceuticals are regarded as independent variables, while the physical characteristics of breast cancer drugs are regarded as dependent variables. Using SPSS software, the regression analyses were performed. The following statistical characteristics are analyzed in Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship (QSPR) analysis: the number of drugs (N), the correlation coefficient (R), the coefficient of determination (R^2), the standard error (SE), Fisher's statistics (F), the p-value, and the root mean square error (RMSE). While the RMSE represents the square root of the average squared discrepancies between the observed and predicted values, the R^2 is a number between 0 and 1, with values nearer 1 denoting greater predictability. A strong fit is usually defined as a multiple linear regression model that has a high R^2 and a low RMSE. The RMSE formula is

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n}}$$

where n is the number of observations, y_i denotes actual values and \hat{y}_i denotes predicted values of the physicochemical properties.

2.5 Multiple Linear Regression Equations for Revan Topological Indices and Physicochemical Properties of Breast Cancer Drugs

This section presents the best-fit multiple linear regression models for the breast cancer drugs' physicochemical properties as determined by QSPR analysis. Table 6 provides a summary of the statistical parameters that correspond to the regression lines.

$$MW = 68.611 - 6.359(R_2(G)) + 0.060(HR_2(G)) - 56.333({}^mR_2(G)) + 1.610(FR(G)) - 3.109(ABCR(G)) + 58.275(GAR(G)) + 2.082(SDR(G))$$

$$BP = 220.147 + 2.847(R_2(G)) - 0.163(HR_2(G)) + 49.096({}^mR_2(G)) + 0.797(FR(G)) + 52.420(ABCR(G)) - 38.653(GAR(G)) - 9.015(SDR(G))$$

$$FP = 36.817 + 0.222(R_2(G)) - 0.034(HR_2(G)) - 20.195({}^mR_2(G)) - 0.062(FR(G)) - 24.038(ABCR(G)) + 21.660(GAR(G)) + 3.697(SDR(G))$$

$$COM = -123.242 - 4.135(R_2(G)) + 0.354(HR_2(G)) - 188.340({}^mR_2(G)) - 3.935(FR(G)) - 128.017(ABCR(G)) + 126.814(GAR(G)) + 40.476(SDR(G))$$

$$EM = 67.973 - 6.349(R_2(G)) + 0.060(HR_2(G)) - 56.298({}^mR_2(G)) + 1.606(FR(G)) - 33.092(ABCR(G)) + 58.237(GAR(G)) + 2.086(SDR(G))$$

$$TPSA = 3.124 - 0.786(R_2(G)) + 0.012(HR_2(G)) - 6.936({}^mR_2(G)) + 0.156(FR(G)) - 4.099(ABCR(G)) + 6.539(GAR(G)) + 1.1132(SDR(G))$$

Table 6 shows that, with the exception of flash point and topological polar surface area, all other properties are well predicted by the multiple linear regression equations since they display a high R^2 values with low RMSE values.

2.6 Revan Topological Indices are compared to Correlation Coefficients of Statistical Parameters and Physicochemical Properties

Six physicochemical properties of the breast cancer drugs taken into consideration in the study are shown in Table 2. The aforementioned degree-based topological indices are calculated and listed in Tables 3 and 4. Table 5 lists the correlation between the topological indices used in this study and each of the six physicochemical properties. The predicted values for the considered drug properties are shown in Table 7 and Figure 2 shows the Comparison of six physicochemical properties' actual and predicted values derived from the topological index regression model.

2.7 MCDM Techniques

A Multi-Criterion Decision-Making technique for evaluating and ranking the compounds according to biological and pharmaceutical criteria is QSPR analysis combined with TOPSIS and VIKOR methods.

2.7.1. TOPSIS Method

Techniques for Multi-Criterion Decision-making to rank 22 drugs for breast cancer, TOPSIS are used. Weighting is distributed evenly when employing the TOPSIS approach. Based on the analysis, the rankings of the 22 examined drugs obtained using the

Table 2. Physicochemical Properties of Breast Cancer Drugs

Drugs	MW	BP	FP	COM	EM	TPSA
Abemaciclib	506.6	689.3	370.7	723	506.27	75
Abraxane	858.9	957.1	532.6	1790	858.36	221
Anastrozole	293.4	469.7	237.9	456	293.16	78.3
Capecitabine	359.35	517	-	582	359.15	121
Cyclophosphamide	261.08	336	113	212	260.02	41.6
Doxorubicin	543.5	-	443.8	977	543.17	206
Everolimus	958.2	998.7	557.8	1810	957.58	205
Exemestane	296.4	453.7	169	653	296.18	34.1
Fluorouracil	130.08	-	-	199	130.02	58.2
Fulvestrant	606.8	674.8	361.9	854	606.32	76.7
Ixabepilone	506.7	697.8	375.8	817	506.28	140
Lapatinib	581.1	750.7	407.8	898	580.13	115
Letrozole	285.3	563.5	294.6	420	285.10	78.3
Megestrol Acetate	384.5	507.1	218.5	820	384.23	60.4
Methotrexate	454.4	561.26	11	704	454.17	211
Olaparib	434.5	-	-	790	434.18	82.1
Docetaxel	807.9	900.5	498.4	1660	807.35	224
Palbociclib	447.5	711.5	384.1	775	447.24	105
Ribociclib	434.5	730.8	395.8	635	434.25	91.2
Talazoparib	380.4	-	-	654	380.12	84.2
Tamoxifen	371.5	501.18	140	463	371.22	12.5
Thiotepa	189.22	270.2	117.2	194	189.05	41.1

Table 3. Topological Index values of Breast Cancer Drugs

Drugs	$R_1(G)$	$R_2(G)$	$HR_1(G)$	$HR_2(G)$	$mR_1(G)$	$mR_2(G)$	$SR(G)$
Abemaciclib	190	176	782	906	15.12	21.556	27.428
Abraxane	327	287	1337	1195	23.867	32.944	44.559
Anastrozole	98	81	392	291	7.4	10.25	13.741
Capecitabine	132	142	626	916	7.41	9.069	14.749
Cyclophosphamide	104	179	760	2697	2.308	1.975	5.833
Doxorubicin	194	177	818	951	17.086	27.458	29.466
Everolimus	366	410	1780	2690	18.788	21.444	38.395
Exemestane	122	99	494	409	10	15.472	17.889
Fluorouracil	46	36	184	124	3.317	4.75	6.256
Fulvestrant	218	227	1044	1443	13.1	18.125	25.112
Ixabepilone	180	169	806	871	11.117	14.722	21.634
Lapatinib	431	774	3259	11438	7.932	4.934	21.407
Letrozole	264	482	1948	6626	4.94	2.764	13.326
MegestrolAcetate	148	121	618	529	11.6	18	20.923
Methotrexate	172	151	692	663	13.267	18.528	24.471
Olaparib	172	158	698	750	13.517	19.25	24.628
Docetaxel	300	259	1250	1091	21.533	30.319	40.235
Palbociclib	176	171	746	947	13.45	19.194	24.521
Ribociclib	168	168	720	956	12.05	16.167	22.516
Talazoparib	146	117	536	415	13.75	20.792	24.064
Tamoxifen	150	147	618	781	11.76	16.139	21.422
Thiotepa	116	239	992	4667	1.752	0.995	4.929

Table 4. Topological Index values of Breast Cancer Drugs

Drugs	PR(G)	FR(G)	ABCR(G)	GAR(G)	HR(G)	SDR(G)
Abemaciclib	31.815	430	33.189	48.38	30.219	126.833
Abraxane	50.952	763	57.268	79.338	47.733	226.833
Anastrozole	15.85	230	18.033	24.131	14.8	71.5
Capecitabine	15.782	342	21.207	28.297	14.819	76.5
Cyclophosphamide	5.102	402	10.429	14.033	4.616	40.6
Doxorubicin	35.806	464	26.683	49.994	34.171	136.333
Everolimus	39.673	960	56.524	76.164	37.576	196.917
Exemestane	21.63	296	20.411	30.106	20	95.75
Fluorouracil	7.364	112	8.703	10.728	6.633	36.75
Fulvestrant	28.147	590	32.385	46.41	26.2	137.667
Ixabepilone	24.251	468	31.067	39.367	22.233	122.5
Lapatinib	16.609	1711	38.013	56.057	15.863	138.167
Letrozole	9.940	984	22.816	35.795	9.881	73.667
MegestrolAcetate	25.326	376	24.602	35.181	23.2	117.667
Methotrexate	28.265	390	31.608	43.103	26.533	119.917
Olaparib	28.453	382	29.306	43.652	27.033	114.417
Docetaxel	46.459	732	52.088	70.913	43.067	216.083
Palbociclib	28.244	404	28.975	43.800	26.9	113.167
Ribociclib	25.292	384	29.186	41.125	24.1	103
Talazoparib	28.914	302	26.370	40.680	27.5	108.417
Tamoxifen	24.211	324	24.825	38.901	23.519	89.917
Thiotepa	3.635	514	8.782	13.598	3.505	31.014

Table 5. Correlation between the Physicochemical Properties and Topological Indices of Breast Cancer Drugs

Drugs	MW	BP	FP	COM	EM	TPSA
$R_1(G)$	0.805	0.649	0.713	0.748	0.805	0.580
$R_2(G)$	0.413	0.446	0.477	0.327	0.170	0.246
$HR_1(G)$	0.465	0.476	0.514	0.385	0.465	0.292
$HR_2(G)$	0.052	0.206	0.220	0.032	0.052	0.035
$mR_1(G)$	0.858	0.443	0.593	0.886	0.736	0.710
$mR_2(G)$	0.730	0.286	0.483	0.781	0.730	0.634
$SR(G)$	0.926	0.542	0.667	0.938	0.926	0.746
$PR(G)$	0.859	0.448	0.593	0.891	0.738	0.713
$FR(G)$	0.512	0.502	0.545	0.437	0.512	0.334
$ABCR(G)$	0.970	0.500	0.717	0.957	0.970	0.750
$GAR(G)$	0.959	0.629	0.733	0.944	0.960	0.744
$HR(G)$	0.858	0.443	0.593	0.886	0.858	0.710
$SDR(G)$	0.959	0.620	0.718	0.972	0.959	0.767

Table 6. Statistical results of MLR models correlating Revan-based topological indices with physicochemical properties of Breast Cancer Drugs

Physicochemical Properties	R	R ²	SE	F	P	RMSE
MW	0.987	0.974	41.024	75.596	0	32.733
BP	0.976	0.952	57.068	28.564	0	38.482
FP	0.824	0.679	116.810	3.024	0.05	78.753
COM	0.990	0.981	77.816	100.776	0	62.087
EM	0.987	0.974	40.901	75.979	0	32.641
TPSA	0.770	0.594	51.302	2.921	0.04	40.925

Table 7. Predicted Values for Physicochemical Properties of Breast Cancer Drugs

Drugs	MW	BP	FP	COM	EM	TPSA
Abemaciclib	465.8841	700.9001	302.1168	738.0126	465.7186	114.7078
Abraxane	887.0307	958.4180	527.7454	1817.1491	886.6748	218.9252
Anastrozole	321.4762	457.8468	177.1820	454.9541	321.2075	71.1908
Capecitabine	366.0221	521.1981	218.8042	530.0398	365.7898	76.2045
Cyclophosphamide	184.6958	345.7692	123.4086	225.3067	184.5604	38.0085
Doxorubicin	513.7297	524.2018	405.9819	926.5133	513.5109	126.6251
Everolimus	936.9563	1010.6959	562.7859	1710.3461	936.6282	199.6816
Exemestane	346.1317	473.9295	229.5241	613.9068	345.8722	88.8484
Fluorouracil	172.9603	335.1376	96.7533	170.2806	172.7329	36.2215
Fulvestrant	559.0479	653.9700	371.2595	1025.4392	558.7369	132.2952
Ixabepilone	490.4602	657.6463	277.1774	845.4481	490.1227	118.0579
Lapatinib	605.1559	745.5324	425.2704	898.2151	605.1003	129.2311
Letrozole	313.1370	580.6349	300.9256	436.8970	313.2470	60.6490
MegestrolAcetate	402.4409	530.8246	264.5235	768.6676	402.1359	108.3423
Methotrexate	446.8844	672.2350	266.5951	736.3245	446.6690	110.4807
Olaparib	450.7979	614.7455	297.9996	775.3740	450.6277	106.6713
Docetaxel	814.9631	893.0972	482.2879	1672.0937	814.5484	207.2332
Palbociclib	435.5068	622.6272	300.4955	725.8812	435.3605	103.5710
Ribociclib	409.4045	654.1785	261.2939	612.5188	409.2667	94.2396
Talazoparib	387.2741	579.6311	258.1269	606.8094	387.1070	97.6247
Tamoxifen	424.9668	549.0257	275.1574	625.4776	424.8161	88.2515
Thiotepa	166.1050	253.5253	77.3247	186.1168	166.0375	31.9952

TOPSIS approach is reported in Table 8. Figure 3 illustrates the weight allocation of TOPSIS method and Figure 4 illustrates the comparison of the TOPSIS ranks.

Fig 2. Comparison between Actual and Predicted Values of MW, BP, FP, COM, EM, and TPSA properties

Fig 3. Weight allocation of TOPSIS Method

Algorithm 1. TOPSIS Method

Step 1: Construction of the decision matrix $X = [x_{ij}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

Step 2: Normalization of the decision matrix $r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$,

Step 3: Construction of the weighted normalized matrix $v_{ij} = w_j \times r_{ij}$, where w_j is the weight of criteria and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Step 4: Determination of ideal best v_j^+ and ideal worst v_j^- solutions

For beneficial criteria: $v_j^+ = \max_i v_{ij}$ and $v_j^- = \min_i v_{ij}$

For non-beneficial criteria: $v_j^+ = \min_i v_{ij}$ and $v_j^- = \max_i v_{ij}$

Step 5: Calculation of separation measures

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}$$

Step 6: Computation of closeness coefficient $P_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-}$

Step 7: Rank the alternatives in descending order of P_i . The highest value of P_i indicates the best alternative.

Table 8. Computed values S_i^+ , S_i^- , P_i and TOPSIS rank of Breast Cancer drugs

Drugs	S_i^+	S_i^-	P_i	TOPSIS RANK
Abemaciclib	0.0363	0.0264	0.4213	8
Abraxane	0.0032	0.0597	0.9488	1
Anastrozole	0.0495	0.0127	0.2048	19
Capecitabine	0.0460	0.0163	0.2620	18
Cyclophosphamide	0.0591	0.0037	0.0589	20
Doxorubicin	0.0322	0.0309	0.4897	6
Everolimus	0.0033	0.0601	0.9477	2
Exemestane	0.0452	0.0171	0.2739	16
Fluorouracil	0.0607	0.0024	0.0385	21
Fulvestrant	0.0290	0.0332	0.5337	5
Ixabepilone	0.0352	0.0271	0.4353	7
Lapatinib	0.0278	0.0354	0.5602	4
Letrozole	0.0475	0.0170	0.2632	17
MegestrolAcetate	0.0401	0.0223	0.3572	12
Methotrexate	0.0379	0.0246	0.3936	10
Olaparib	0.0374	0.0249	0.3992	9
Docetaxel	0.0082	0.0544	0.8685	3
Palbociclib	0.0384	0.0241	0.3852	11
Ribociclib	0.0413	0.0215	0.3425	13
Talazoparib	0.0423	0.0202	0.3233	15
Tamoxifen	0.0416	0.0209	0.3341	14
Thiotepa	0.0620	0.0003	0.0047	22

2.7.2. VIKOR Method

A technique for Multi-Criterion Decision-making to rank 22 drugs for breast cancer, VIKOR is used. In VIKOR, weighting is determined by the ratio approach for the indices that are taken into consideration in the study. According to the analysis, 22 drugs are evaluated, and Table 9 illustrates the rankings that VIKOR provided for the properties of MW. A comprehensive analysis of VIKOR's rankings for each drug in relation to the study's features is presented in Table 10. The weight distribution

Fig 4. TOPSIS Rank comparison

of the VIKOR technique for the properties of MW against the indices taken into consideration is shown in Figure 5. Other properties are also analyzed with comparable weight allocation. Figure 6 clearly illustrates that the comparison of VIKOR rankings for the considered drugs.

Table 9. Calculated values S_i , R_i , Q_i and VIKOR rank of MW

Drugs	S_i	R_i	Q_i	VIKOR RANK
Abemaciclib	0.5097	0.0538	0.3994	4
Abraxane	0.1216	0.0326	0.0298	1
Anastrozole	0.8038	0.0840	0.7723	19
Capecitabine	0.7694	0.0783	0.7143	18
Cyclophosphamide	0.9341	0.1003	0.9566	20
Doxorubicin	0.4699	0.0655	0.4526	6
Everolimus	0.2203	0.0281	0.0584	2
Exemestane	0.7108	0.0789	0.6837	16
Fluorouracil	0.9663	0.1040	1	22
Fulvestrant	0.5274	0.0533	0.4063	5
Ixabepilone	0.61	0.0594	0.4956	11
Lapatinib	0.4476	0.0684	0.4584	7
Letrozole	0.7108	0.0798	0.6893	17
MegestrolAcetate	0.6367	0.0700	0.5807	14
Methotrexate	0.5701	0.0579	0.4616	8
Olaparib	0.5722	0.0599	0.4762	9
Docetaxel	0.2064	0.0337	0.0871	3
Palbociclib	0.5714	0.0606	0.4804	10
Ribociclib	0.6131	0.0645	0.5308	12
Talazoparib	0.5946	0.0662	0.5309	13
Tamoxifen	0.6489	0.0713	0.5969	15
Thiotepa	0.9404	0.1038	0.9836	21

Fig 5. VIKOR Method: Weights allocation of MW

Table 10. VIKOR Rank of all properties

Drugs	MW	BP	FP	COM	EM	TPSA
Abemaciclib	4	7	7	4	4	4
Abraxane	1	2	2	1	1	1
Anastrozole	19	19	19	19	19	19
Capecitabine	18	18	18	18	18	18
Cyclophosphamide	20	20	20	20	20	20
Doxorubicin	6	6	6	6	6	6
Everolimus	2	1	1	3	2	3
Exemestane	16	17	17	16	16	16
Fluorouracil	22	22	22	21	22	21
Fulvestrant	5	5	5	5	5	5
Ixabepilone	11	10	11	10	11	10
Lapatinib	7	4	4	11	8	12
Letrozole	17	14	16	17	17	17
MegestrolAcetate	14	15	14	14	14	14
Methotrexate	8	9	9	7	7	7
Olaparib	9	11	10	8	9	8
Docetaxel	3	3	3	2	3	2
Palbociclib	10	8	8	9	10	9
Ribociclib	12	12	12	13	13	13
Talazoparib	13	13	13	12	12	11
Tamoxifen	15	16	15	15	15	15
Thiotepa	21	21	21	22	21	22

Fig 6. VIKOR Rank of all properties

Algorithm 2. VIKOR MethodStep 1: Determination of ideal best f_j^+ and ideal worst f_j^- values

For beneficial criteria:

$$f_j^+ = \max_i f_{ij} \text{ and } f_j^- = \min_i f_{ij}$$

For non-beneficial criteria:

$$f_j^+ = \min_i f_{ij} \text{ and } f_j^- = \max_i f_{ij}$$

Step 2: Computation of the utility measure S_i and regret measure R_i

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \left(\frac{f_j^+ - f_{ij}}{f_j^+ - f_j^-} \right) \text{ and } R_i = \max_j \left[w_j \left(\frac{f_j^+ - f_{ij}}{f_j^+ - f_j^-} \right) \right]$$

Step 3: Determination of the VIKOR index Q_i

$$Q_i = v \left(\frac{S_i - S^+}{S^- - S^+} \right) + (1 - v) \left(\frac{R_i - R^+}{R^- - R^+} \right)$$

where $S^+ = \min_i S_i$, $S^- = \max_i S_i$, $R^+ = \min_i R_i$, $R^- = \max_i R_i$ and $v \in [0, 1]$ represent the weights of the majority criteria (usually $v = 0.5$).

Step 4: Ranking of alternatives

Rank the alternatives in ascending order of Q_i . The smallest Q_i corresponds to the best compromise solution.**3 Result and Discussion**

The computed Revan-type topological indices were analyzed using Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) models to predict several physicochemical properties of twenty-two breast cancer drugs. The developed models demonstrated good predictive ability. Of all the properties, complexity had the highest correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.981$). Molecular weight and exact mass also

showed strong predictive performance with $R^2 = 0.974$, while boiling point reached $R^2 = 0.952$. Flash point and TPSA had moderate correlations with $R^2 = 0.679$ and $R^2 = 0.594$, respectively. The statistical measures, including p -values and RMSE values, confirm the reliability and significance of the developed regression models. The results compare well with earlier QSPR studies on breast cancer drugs reported in the literature. Shanmukha et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ used linear regression models, while Altassan et al.⁽¹¹⁾ used cubic regression and MLR techniques. Their boiling point model reported $R^2 = 0.838$, but this study achieved a higher value of $R^2 = 0.952$. Compared to the work of Pandeewari and Ravi Sankar⁽¹⁶⁾, where the MLR model produced $R = 0.366$ for predicting polar surface area, this study showed improved predictive performance for TPSA analysis with $R = 0.770$. The TOPSIS and VIKOR analyses produced nearly the same ranking patterns for the breast cancer drugs investigated. In both decision-making methods, Abraxane, Everolimus, and Docetaxel held the highest ranks, indicating better physicochemical properties and overall predictive performance. In contrast, Thiotepa and Fluorouracil ranked lower in both models. The agreement between the two methods shows that the proposed computational framework is stable and reliable. These findings demonstrate that combining Revan-type topological indices, multiple linear regression, TOPSIS, and VIKOR techniques can effectively assess breast cancer drugs. Unlike many previous studies that treated all chemical bonds as single edges, this work considers single, double, and triple bonds as separate edges in molecular graphs. Therefore, the proposed approach provides a more detailed structural representation and offers improved predictive analysis of breast cancer drugs.

4 Conclusion

In this research, Revan-type topological indices were examined for twenty-two breast cancer medications using adjusted molecular graph structures. The calculated descriptors were utilized in Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis to predict various physicochemical properties. The models developed exhibited satisfactory predictive capabilities. Among the properties analyzed, complexity yielded the highest correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.981$), while molecular weight and exact mass resulted in $R^2 = 0.974$. Additionally, the boiling point model demonstrated strong predictive accuracy with $R^2 = 0.952$. In comparison to previous studies, this work showcases enhanced predictive performance for boiling point and TPSA evaluations. The TOPSIS and VIKOR methods yielded similar ranking outcomes, with Abraxane, Everolimus, and Docetaxel attaining the top ranks in both analyses. The consistency between the ranking methods affirms the reliability of the results. The novelty of this study lies in considering bond multiplicity during molecular graph construction instead of treating all chemical bonds uniformly as single edges. Overall, the findings show that Revan-type topological indices combined with MLR, TOPSIS, and VIKOR methods provide an effective approach for QSPR analysis and comparative evaluation of breast cancer drugs. This approach could be extended to larger datasets and machine learning models in future research.

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6 Contributory Statement

K. M. Saranya: Conceptualization, Experimental Design, Software/Algorithm, Data Generation, Data Analysis, Original Drafting; Dr.S. Manimekalai: Experimental Design, Research Guidance, Editing & Reviewing.

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